

Energy Demand Research Centre's response to DESNZ consultation on: Reforms to the Energy Performance of Buildings regime

About EDRC

EDRC (the Energy Demand Research Centre) aims to inform and inspire energy demand reductions that support an affordable, comfortable and secure Net Zero society. Collaborating with partners across policy, industry, civil society and academia, EDRC will deliver a world-leading transformative and interdisciplinary research programme that identifies and shapes evidence-based energy demand solutions for a sustainable and more equitable future. The Energy Demand Research Centre is supported by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council and the Economic and Social Research Council [grant number EP/Y010078/1].

This response was written on behalf of UoR E&EERG and EDRC by:

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Background and General Comments

In the UK, the concept of Energy Performance Certification was first introduced more than 20 years ago. A lot has changed since so this consultation on the EPB regime reform is a most welcome development.

EDRC supports wholeheartedly the initiative and the effort devoted to it so far, and we look forward to engaging further with DESNZ to make these reforms a reality.

A single metric like the current Energy Efficiency Rating has proved to be insufficient to meet the diverse needs of users and policy objectives.

It is, therefore, encouraging to see that the government is responding to this by proposing using multiple metrics on EPCs to provide a more complete representation of building energy performance.

In this consultation, the government wants to understand the potential of a range of metrics that could be used in EPCs.

Among the metrics considered thus far, there is a “Smart readiness” component which looks at assessing a building’s potential to integrate smart technologies that can optimise energy consumption and the ability of consumers to benefit from cheaper smart tariffs.

Given our expertise, we will focus our attention on this “smart readiness” component, as we believe this is where our insight is most relevant.

Questions

Q7 - What are your views on the definition, design principles and the scope for a smart readiness metric? Please provide evidence where possible.

Future-proofing the EPC framework will indeed require the introduction of metrics such as the suggested “smart readiness” one.

In future, and in the broader context of the transition to a Net Zero economy, it would be in the Government’s best interest to ensure that the new metrics address some of the key barriers to such transition.

A building’s “smart readiness” rating can serve as a useful proxy metric to address some of the shortcomings of the current EPC methodology.

However, we would argue that the extent to which this metric will prove useful will depend on the attributes it is meant to assess.

Energy demand flexibility will play an increasingly important role in the decarbonisation of the energy system. The Clean Power 2030 Action Plan estimates that energy demand flexibility should grow 4-5 times to reach 10-12 GW by 2030.¹

Currently, the main obstacle to the realisation of the benefits of harnessing energy demand flexibility is that there is a general lack of visibility of available flexibility.

A way of solving this would involve the implementation of a standardised framework for the quantification of the demand flexibility that could be provided by each dwelling/building, and using metrics that explicitly capture this and adequately inform key stakeholders such as energy system and market operators.

We recognise the value of the concept of “Smart readiness”. However, we would also contend that the development of a metric with a focus on capturing a building’s “smart readiness” or its “potential to integrate smart technologies” would run the risk of being too broad, too subjective, and not clear/explicit enough for some of the key purposes that, in our view, this kind of metric would/should aim to facilitate.

For instance, knowing that a building is, say, 50% “smart ready” would still not provide a demand flexibility user/aggregator with enough information to place/validate any bids to trade flexibility. That is partly because the “smartness” of a building may refer to its ability to sense, interpret, communicate, and respond to wider system signals, or more likely, a combination of all these factors, in which case, the meaning of the overall rating for any of these specific factors is obscured.

“Smart” technologies will, no doubt, play a key role in enhancing a building’s performance. However, in the context of the quantification of the overall demand flexibility potential, technological innovations are only a part of the elements that need to be factored in.

In order for the smart readiness metric to meaningfully ‘*optimize energy usage, reduce demand during peak periods, and help evaluate a building’s demand response capabilities*’,² we suggest that the scope for such metric should include the characteristics identified in the EDRC report on Demand Flexibility Certification framework³ and summarised in our answer to question 7a.

7a) - How should a smart readiness metric be defined, and what relevant characteristics of the building and appliances should be considered?

We believe there is still significant value in developing this kind of metric with a view to providing an explicit account of the demand flexibility potential of the building, should this be required.

That is, in addition to the “headline rating” that is likely to be publicly available as is the case for current EERs, we believe that there is a strong case for providing key stakeholders with a more detailed view of the elements behind said headline rating. For example, DNOs would benefit from an explicit account of the demand flexibility potential, as well as the total capacity of any on-site microgeneration assets.

¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/clean-power-2030-action-plan>

² Technical annex for chapter 2: What EPCs measure

³ <https://www.edrc.ac.uk/publications/demand-flexibility-certificates/>

The smart readiness metric should rate the Demand Flexibility potential across two key dimensions: magnitude and quality.

We focus on these two dimensions primarily with the aim of providing an overview that is informative and meaningful enough, and provides an adequate level of nuance, but at the same time, does not add too much complexity to the rating system.

We propose a Nominal rating which corresponds to the overall magnitude of the demand increase/decrease that could be delivered [kW], whereas the Quality rating provides an indication of how readily the Demand Flexibility potential can be harnessed, and is a function of factors such as how often, how fast, and for how long can the flexible demand responses be delivered (i.e. response rate [kW/second], frequency [events/day], and duration [minutes]).

7b) - Should the metric focus solely on smart building systems, or should it also include smart domestic appliances?

Some companies are beginning to offer smart services and tariffs to consumers. However, these are often limited to specific devices (e.g. smart heating and EVs), restricting consumer choice and creating barriers to broader market participation.

A smart readiness metric aimed at optimizing energy usage, reducing peak demand, and assessing a building's demand response capabilities should **not** focus solely on smart building systems.

Including smart domestic appliances is essential to ensure a more integrated and effective approach to demand flexibility. By incorporating smart appliances into the metric, a more competitive and dynamic market can emerge, enabling consumers to access a wider range of services. Achieving this requires the establishment of common metrics, as well as co-ordinated Government action to complete the Energy Smart Appliance standardisation process.⁴

7c) - How can we distinguish between different tiers of smart readiness, associating them with specific functionalities and technologies to create a practical framework for evaluation?

Setting considerations aside of whether “smart readiness” is the most suitable metric – which we don't necessarily think it is – it is worth pointing out that this is not an inherent property that can, or will ever be, directly measurable.

Therefore, it is important to establish the key elements that will feed into any assessment of the state of “readiness”, and make every effort to strictly define what this “readiness” means in order to limit the ambiguities that can arise from using this type of metric.

⁴ PAS 1878 - Energy Smart Appliances - System Functionality and Architecture (<https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/insights-and-media/insights/brochures/pas-1878-energy-smart-appliances-system-functionality-and-architecture/>)

In an ideal scenario, the “smart readiness” metric would be a proxy for real, directly measurable properties.

The performance of a given building would then be mapped across these key properties, which will then provide a better indication of the tiers, on the basis of meaningful or significant enough differences across the building stock.

An example of this kind of approach can be found in our proposed methodology for the systematic assessment of the Demand Flexibility potential at the building level.⁵

Rather than focusing on “smart readiness,” what is truly needed is a Demand Flexibility Metric — a systematic framework that assesses a building’s ability to adjust energy use in response to grid conditions. A Demand Flexibility Certification would enable building owners and operators to identify opportunities for enhancing their flexibility potential, serving as a crucial first step in engaging with flexibility markets.

Mapping this potential at local, regional, and national levels would provide critical insights for system planning, helping to optimize network reinforcement and investment decisions. By establishing a standardised way to evaluate and communicate a building’s flexibility value, such a metric would create a more efficient and transparent market, benefiting both providers and users of demand flexibility.

⁵ <https://www.edrc.ac.uk/publications/demand-flexibility-certificates/>

Rating Component	Metrics [units]
Basal flexibility	Building cool-down profile Internal temperature recovery
Heating/cooling flexibility	Heating/cooling system performance Heating/cooling system power ratings Thermal stores' performance
Technology-enabled flexibility	Dedicated electric storage performance

Rating Component	Metrics [units]
Basal flexibility	Temperature recovery rate (°C/hour:min)
Heating/cooling flexibility	Coefficient of Performance (kWh/m ²) Power draw (kW) Storage capacity (kWh/m ²) Heat loss rate (kWh/m ² h) Power draw (kW)
Technology-enabled flexibility	Storage capacity (kWh/m ²) Charge/discharge rate (C-rate) Degradation rate (% capacity loss/cycle)

Figure 1 – Visual representation of the process for the systematic assessment of the Demand Flexibility potential of a Building/Dwelling.

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